

Mondaecus short User Guide

(V0.1)

1. Access & Login

- **Step-by-step login instructions.**

1. Access the platform's website: <https://mondaecus.com/>
2. In the top-right corner, you will find the option for the English version.

3. Choose your authentication method.

4. Enter your credentials:

Email: the address you used to register

Password: your chosen password

Click **“Login”** to access your account

2. Dashboard Overview

- **Description of main interface:**
 - Home page

- Navigation bar / menus

In the **top-left corner**, you will find the **navigation bar** and the **menus**:

At the **centre** of the Home Page are the two main **quick-access functions**: Communities and Documents.

3. Working on a Translation Project

- **Opening a project.**
 - In the **left-hand sidebar**, click on **“Documents.”**

Here you can:

- Upload your DOCX or PDF file
- Create a **New Document**
- Give your document a title
- Select the original language (e.g. “English”)
 - How to select the right **project / language group**.
 - Viewing source language (English)
 - Target language fields.
- **Entering translations:**
 - On the **right-hand sidebar**, click the **third button** (translation icon): **Create New Translation**

To create a translation, the original version must be locked. The platform will ask, and you should agree and **Continue**.

- Choose the target language.

- A new translation version will be created, while the original document is locked. The editor now shows the original text side-by-side with the translation blocks.

- An AI Translation button is available on the platform, allowing you to generate an automatic draft translation of the selected document. This feature can be used to speed up the initial translation process before human review and refinement.

- you can Use the “**Translate all**” button to generate a machine translation draft (if supported).

- Multiple translations of the same document can exist simultaneously.

- Each translation has workflow states: **Draft** → **Under Review** → **Published**.

- Editing and saving changes.

4. Collaboration Features

- How to add comments or notes.

Inside the document, click on the second icon in the top right corner, and select “New Comment”

- **Real-time editing:** multiple users can write simultaneously, with changes appearing instantly.
- **Block-level comments:** every paragraph/content block has its own comment thread, enabling discussion and review.
- **Assigning or dividing tasks within the group.**
 - On the **right-hand sidebar**, click the **fourth button (cog/settings icon)** → **“Share Document.”**
 - **Private sharing:** Invite collaborators by email and assign roles:
 - **Viewer:** can only read
 - **Reviewer:** can read and comment
 - **Editor:** can edit text
 - **Manager:** full control, including settings and permissions
 - **Share via link:** enable a read-only share link for wider access.

- **Community sharing:** Move the document into a community (see below).
- Documents can be shared privately or moved into communities, allowing group co-authoring before translation.
- Tips for consistency (use of glossaries, agreement on terminology).

5. Creating and managing communities:

- In the left-hand sidebar, click “My Communities.”

- Press “**New Community**”, give it a **title and description**, and press **Create**.

Community features:

- Each community includes:
 - A **chat space** for discussion
 - **File storage**, which can hold editor documents, translations, and any additional resources (DOCX, PDFs, PowerPoints, etc.). You can also create folders to keep files organized.
- By default, communities are **closed**:
 - They are publicly searchable, but new members must request access, and only the community owner can approve them.

- You can also add members manually in the **Members tab** by pressing “**Add Member**” and searching the Mondaecus user database.
- If you prefer an **open community**, click the **cogs icon** next to the community name and switch on “**Automatically accept join requests.**” This allows anyone to join without approval.
- From this settings page, you can also:
 - Upload a **logo and cover image**
 - Edit the community **name and description**
 - Adjust visibility and participation rules.

6. Export & Review

- How final translations are validated.

This model allows the translation to evolve as a **living document**, each translated text block can be commented on, reviewed, and approved by the members of the same group.

- How documents/outputs can be exported or downloaded.

To export a document, click on the fourth button in the top right corner, and “**Share document**” will appear; at the moment, it is only possible to export to HTML:

The screenshot shows the Mondaecus web interface for a document titled 'hackathon_test'. The interface is in 'Edition mode' and displays a translation of a document from English to German. The left sidebar shows a list of categories under 'B1', including 'Archaeology and Prehistory', 'Architecture and Space Management', 'Art and Art History', 'Biological Anthropology', 'Classical Studies', 'Communication Sciences', 'Cultural Heritage and Museology', 'Demography', 'Economies and Finances', 'Education', 'Environmental studies', 'Gender Studies', 'Geography', 'History', 'History, Philosophy and Sociology of Sciences', and 'Law'. The main content area shows the translated text 'Etiketten' under the category 'B1'. The right sidebar contains 'Settings' for the document, including 'Page title' (hackathon_test), 'Share and permissions', and 'Export document' options, with a prominent 'Share document' button and an 'HTML file' export option.

7. Best Practices & Tips

- Keep translations concise and consistent.
- Collaborate actively (comment, discuss, agree).
- Use auriculares/headphones for smooth communication.
- Save regularly and double-check before submitting.

8. Troubleshooting & FAQs

- Common technical issues (slow system, edits not saving, login fails).
- Browser requirements and device compatibility.
- Troubleshooting login (lost password, no access).

9. Contacts & Support

- Mondaecus team contact:

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